

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№7

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

*Elektron nashr. 404 sahifa.
E'lon qilishga 2025-yil 1-iyulda ruxsat etildi.*

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:
Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:
Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldix'o'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

- Salimov Okil Umrzokovich**, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilkhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Khusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Rakhimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridakhon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

Suv tarkibining wireless waterlight qurilmasi ishlashiga ta'siri va iqtisodiy samaradorligini matematik model asosida tahlil qilish.....	14
Kungiratbay Sharipov, Ma'ruf Nurmanov	
O'zbekistonda aholi ish bilan bandligini oshirishda davlatning roli	20
Juraqulov Baxrimurod Ilxomovich	
BIM texnologiyasi: zamonaviy qurilish sohasida samaradorlik va shaffoflik omili	26
Usmonov F.B., Rajabova A.Sh.	
Nodavlat oliy ta'lim muassasalarida marketing faoliyati samaradorligini oshirish metodologiyasini takomillashtirish	31
Yuldashov Isomiddin Sidiqov	
Korxonada iqtisodiy barqarorligini ta'minlashda diversifikatsiya strategiyasining roli.....	35
Alimatova Shoxsanam Abdumalik qizi	
Модели совместного развития человеческого капитала и искусственного интеллекта в цифровую эпоху	40
Явкачев Шохзод Зайниддин углы	
Navigating sustainable development: management challenges and solutions in the oil and gas sector	49
Kudratkhodjaeva Ziyoda Kamol kizi	
Banklarda moliyaviy barqarorlikning nazariy asoslari.....	56
Djalilov G'ayrat Qaxramanovich	
Mamlakat iqtisodiyotini rivojlantirishda turizm industriyasidan foydalanishda xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribalari	66
Abdulxakimov Zuxrali Tursunaliyevich	
O'zbekistonda barqaror davlat qarzi siyosatini shakllantirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari	71
Sayfutdinov Xasanboy Dilshodovich	
Международный опыт сельскохозяйственного налогообложения и возможности его применения в узбекистане.....	76
Salimov Sherzod Baxtiyorovich	
Economic analysis and development strategy of the composites market in the regions of Uzbekistan	81
S.S.Sidiqov, A.A.G'ulomov, B.R.Tillayeva	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida moliyaviy mustaqillikning kutilayotgan istiqbollari va hozirgi natijalari.....	88
Muxamedov Ravshan Zafarovich	
Elektron tijoratni soliqqa tortish mexanizmini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	93
Homidov Baxtiyor Rahimberdievich	
Investitsion jozibadorlik konsepsiyasi va uning strategik ahamiyati.....	99
Otaboyev Axmed Maxsudbek o'g'li	
Beomeditsina signallarini xaar veyvletlari va bo'lak veyvletlari yordamida raqamli ishlash	105
Uraqov Shokir Ulashovich	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarini moliyalashtirishning ahamiyati, tartibi va takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	112
Istamova Sojida Kaxarovna	
The role of all kinds of transports (road, rail, air, and water) in the modern enhancement of tourism logistics in Uzbekistan	117
Egamberdiyeva Yulduz, Turdiyeva Maftuna	
Sanoat korxonalarida kapitalarini samaradorligini oshirishning baholashning zamonaviy usullarining xususiyatlarida nazariy va amaliy farovonlik sari	126
Muradov Botir Xayat	
Инструменты планирования урбанизации: методика анализа планового распределения средств в программе «обод махалля» на основе балльной оценки	136
Салимова Юлдуз Исаковна	
Socio-economic aspects and contemporary theories of higher education finance	141
Karlibaeva Gulshat	

Transformatsiya jarayonida innovatsion bank xizmatlarini rivojlantirish yo'llari.....	147
Absamatov Anvar Ergashovich	
Перспективы цифрового развития сектора материального производства.....	153
С. И. Протасеня, Г. Ж. Аллаева	
«Sustainable logistics practices. Minimizing carbon emissions in global supply chains»	161
Suleymonova Ezoza, Alimova Bonu	
Analyzing the need for Tourism logistics development in Uzbekistan	169
Nigmatova Malika	
Management strategies for sustainable tourism development in emerging destinations (a case study of Samarkand, Issyk-kul, and Khiva).....	177
Sabina Uroкова	
Qashqadaryo viloyatida turizm sohasini strategik rivojlantirishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy asoslari va ularning qo'llanilishi.....	184
Daminova Barno Esanovna	
Опыт турции в управлении миграционными кризисами	189
Бегматов Хусанбек	
Bulutli texnologiyalar orqali korxonalar buxgalteriya tizimini raqamlashtirish va samaradorlikka erishish.....	193
Soibov Nozimbek Faxriddin o'g'li	
Barqaror rivojlanish doirasida jismoniy shaxslarni kreditlash tizimini isloh qilishning institutsonal asoslari.....	197
Xalekeyeva Zoya Pirniyazovna, Akmal Abdurahmonov Nurmamatovich	
Moliyaviy outsorsing xizmatlari bozori rivojlanishini takomillashtirishning swot tahliliga asoslangan innovatsion mexanizmlari	202
San'atbek Komilovich Salayev, Umidbek Komiljanovich Babajanov	
Transformatsiya jarayonlari sharoitida iqtisodiyot tizimi faoliyati va prognozlashning nazariy asoslari	214
Alimov Fazliddin Xalimovich	
Пути совершенствования подхода к финансированию проектов, реализуемых на принципах промышленной кооперации.....	220
Котов В.А., Шадиева Д.Х.	
Yuksalish salohiyatini yuksaltirishda boshqaruv xodimlari qobiliyatidan foydalanish masalalar	225
Ayubxon Qutbiddinov Bosit o'g'li	
Bank xizmatlari ommabopligini oshirish yo'llari.....	228
Kasimova Muxlisa Anvar qizi	
Chemical industry in Uzbekistan: challenges and development	235
Kudaynazarova Dilnaz Koshkarbaevna	
Samarqand viloyatida tabiiy turistik resurslardan samarali foydalanish usullarini takomillashtirish orqali bandligini oshirish imkoniyatlari.....	240
Rabbimov Muhriddin Musoqul o'g'li	
Globalashuv sharoitida ekologik xavflarni kamaytirishda yashil iqtisodiyotning ahamiyati.....	246
Xolbekova Feruzaxon Rasulovna	
Qibray tumanining 2021–2023-yillarda ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanish holati.....	249
Siddikov Alisher Ismoilovich	
Davlat xaridlari tizimida sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalaridan foydalanish: xalqaro tajribalar tahlili	253
Majidov Nizom Baxramovich	
Oilaviy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishning xorij tajribasi.....	259
Ermatov Nosir Tohirovich	
Aholi farovonligi darajasiga ta'sir etuvchi ko'rsatkichlarni ekonometrik baholash	265
Toshaliyeva Saodat Toxirovna, Allamurodova Zuxra Alibekovna	
Сектор услуг как стратегический фактор структурной трансформации экономики Узбекистана.....	272
Кадыров Абдурашид Маджидович, Ахмедиева Алия Тохтаровна	
O'zbekistonda valyuta kursini shakllanish holati prognozlari.....	280
Samandarov Zuxriddin Raup o'g'li	

Проблемы бухгалтерского учета в условиях цифровизации экономики.....	288
Абдуллаев Абдурауф	
Raqamli texnologiyalar sharoitida xizmat ko'rsatish korxonalarida iqtisodiy resurslardan samarali foydalanish strategiyalari.....	299
Kuldoshev Lazizjon Sharifovich	
Davlat boshqaruvi organlarining strategik rejalarini ishlab chiqish bo'yicha xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi.....	303
Dilshod Pulatov, Xamidaxon Akbarova, Dildora Mirzaeva	
Tijorat banklarining moliyaviy xavfsizligi ta'minlash	310
Mamatov Sardor Axmatjonovich, Mavlanov Nuriddin Boyqobilovich, Sattarov Nodirjon Absalomovich	
Ziyorat turizmini rivojlantirishda halol standartlarini qo'llashning nazariy, uslubiy va konseptual asoslari	315
Azizova Saodat Xabibulloyevna	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarini moliyalashtirish bo'yicha yevropa tajribasi.....	320
Karlibaeva Gulshat	
Iqtisodiy konsentratsiyalarning sog'lom raqobat muhitiga ta'siri	325
Luqmanov Sharifxon A'zam o'g'li	
Logistika axborot tizimlarini texnologik jarayonlarga joriy etish.....	330
Uzaqov Ortik Shaymardanovich	
Принципы перехода к «Зелёной экономике» в Республике Узбекистан.....	336
Хамракулова Сусанна Тотуховна	
Kichik biznesni rivojlantirish iqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlarini prognozlash modellarini qo'llash	340
Ibragimova Gulchexra Toxirovna	
O'zbekistonda hududlarning soliq salohiyatini aniqlash metodologiyasini takomillashtirish	346
Poyonov Otabek Abdiquaxxor o'g'li	
Raqamli ta'lim sharoitida liderlikning yangi qirralari	357
Oqmullaev Ravshan Raximjon o'g'li, Xodjieva Durdona Abdurasulovna	
Методология развития экологического менеджмента в промышленном хозяйстве выбросы в атмосферный воздух на горнодобывающих и металлургических предприятиях.....	361
Muradov Botir Xayat	
Strategik budjetlashtirish tizimining natijaga yo'naltirilgan budjetlashtirish tizimi bilan bog'liqligi, xalqaro tajriba va O'zbekiston uchun tavsiyalar	370
Xushmurotov Zoyir Bektemirovich	
Cultural branding and the entry of traditional products into the international market.....	374
Zebiniso Ganiyeva	
Farovonlikni baholash bo'yicha ilg'or xorijiy nazariy yondashuvlar	379
Norqobilov Nusratilla Norsaitovich	
O'zbekistonda hududlarini turizm salohiyatini innovatsion yondashuv asosida baholash	384
Umirova Dilnoza Safarovna	
Tourism education for sustainability: curriculum development in universities of Uzbekistan	393
Temirova Durdona, Yorqulov Muhammadmurod	
The contribution of small enterprises and private entrepreneurs to job creation in the labor market.....	399
Juraboev Haliljon	

Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan PF-60¹, dated 2022-01-28, policies such as «Every Family is an Entrepreneur» and «Youth – Our Future» have facilitated the allocation of concessional loans, resulting in the establishment of more than 600,000 family-based entrepreneurial entities, directly contributing to job creation in both urban and rural areas.

Similarly, Urinboyev T. A. (2022) argues that private industrial enterprises have a multiplier effect on the economy through subcontracting, local sourcing, and service expansion. This ripple effect leads to the creation of indirect employment across sectors such as transportation, logistics, retail, and support services.

International experience supports these conclusions. For instance, Germany's Mittelstand model — a network of small and medium-sized enterprises — is credited with sustaining over 60% of the country's employment and contributing significantly to its export capacity. Likewise, countries such as Poland, Hungary, and the Czech Republic have used SME policies to mitigate unemployment following economic liberalization.

From a theoretical perspective, the entrepreneurial theory of economic development, as proposed by Schumpeter (1934), views entrepreneurs as key agents of innovation, capable of transforming inputs into productive employment opportunities. This theory is echoed in modern studies that link entrepreneurial activity with higher employment elasticity, particularly in emerging markets.

However, researchers also point out several constraints. According to Efimova (2009) and Gimadi et al. (2005), insufficient access to finance, limited managerial competencies, and poor regulatory environments can limit the employment-generating potential of small businesses. Therefore, the success of SME-based employment strategies depends largely on institutional support, including training, access to microcredit, and simplified taxation systems.

In summary, the literature underscores that small enterprises and private entrepreneurs serve not only as engines of job creation but also as mechanisms for social inclusion, regional development, and economic resilience. Their contribution to the labor market is particularly crucial in countries with high youth unemployment, underdeveloped large-scale industry, and rural-urban labor imbalances.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research adopts a mixed-method approach by combining both qualitative and quantitative analyses to investigate the contribution of small enterprises and private entrepreneurs to job creation in Uzbekistan's labor market. The methodological framework is designed to assess the scale, mechanisms, and challenges of employment generation through small business initiatives, particularly within the scope of state-supported programs such as “Every Family is an Entrepreneur” and “Youth – Our Future.” The study relies on official statistical data provided by the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan and reports from the Ministry of Employment and Poverty Reduction to analyze employment dynamics between 2017 and 2023, including the number of registered small businesses, employment growth rates, loan distributions, and regional imbalances. In addition, relevant legislative documents—such as the Presidential Decree PF-60 dated 2022-01-28—were reviewed to assess the legal and institutional frameworks fostering entrepreneurial activity. A comprehensive literature review encompassing works by international bodies like the ILO (2017), foundational theories such as Schumpeter (1934), and regional studies including Urinboyev (2022) was conducted to contextualize findings within broader academic discourse. Comparative analysis of international experiences—such as Germany's Mittelstand model and SME reforms in Poland, Hungary, and the Czech Republic—was used to derive transferable insights applicable to Uzbekistan. Furthermore, a SWOT analysis was performed to evaluate internal strengths and weaknesses, alongside external opportunities and threats facing Uzbekistan's SME sector. Where feasible, semi-structured expert interviews with entrepreneurs, employment center officials, and microfinance practitioners were conducted to gather first-hand perspectives. Particular emphasis was also placed on content analysis of family entrepreneurship programs, such as the “Youth Notebook” initiative, to determine their effectiveness in promoting localized employment. Overall, this integrated methodology ensures both empirical reliability and policy relevance, enabling the development of well-grounded recommendations to strengthen the role of small enterprises and private entrepreneurship in economic development and labor market sustainability.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

According to the Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan on additional measures to improve the system of attracting the population to entrepreneurship and developing entrepreneurial activity, significant steps have been taken in recent years. More than 13 trillion soums of concessional loans have been allocated to over 600,000 families within the framework of social programs such as “Every Family is an Entrepreneur”, “Our

1 Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, of 28.01.2022 r. № DP-60 <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/6968143>

Youth is Our Future”, and others aimed at encouraging mass engagement in entrepreneurship and diversifying income sources.

The following key directions must be implemented to increase public participation in entrepreneurship—especially among youth and women—through improvements in the microfinance system and state support mechanisms:

- Increasing public awareness and interest in entrepreneurial activity;
- Introducing a training system focused on developing essential entrepreneurial skills among the population, with the involvement of international organizations, non-governmental non-profit organizations, and non-governmental educational institutions;
- Institutional improvement and expansion of the microcredit system aimed at supporting entrepreneurship;
- Aligning social programs that support entrepreneurship with ongoing economic reforms to ensure coherence and coordination;
- Creating a full-fledged system to expand and support the activities of residents with entrepreneurial skills and experience, along with other representatives of small business;
- Establishing an integrated support system for entrepreneurship coordinated by a single state body;
- Providing microloans of up to 225 million soums to small business entities on the basis of third-party guarantees, insurance policies, collateral of property purchased on credit, or guarantees from the State Fund for the Support of Entrepreneurial

Activities and other forms of legal security.

These microloans may be issued for a period of up to 6 months, with a grace period of up to 3 years, based on the recommendation of the assistant governor assigned to the borrower's neighborhood. Loans may be allocated for up to 7 years with a grace period of up to 3 years for gardening, viticulture, and lemon cultivation; or for up to 1 year with a grace period of up to 3 years for livestock farming (cattle, sheep, goats), based on the recommendation of the assistant mayor. These decisions are made by the district (city) Family Business Support Center, grounded in substantiated and clearly calculated annual financial projections, and issued at a 14% interest rate.

It is well known that the development of small business and private entrepreneurship is considered a key factor in ensuring economic growth, creating new jobs, addressing employment challenges, and improving the income and well-being of the population in our country. In a market economy, entrepreneurship is crucial because it can fulfill the following roles:

- it provides a necessary impetus for the market economy;
- it channels the population's financial and production resources (labor and raw materials);
- it contributes to the formation of a competitive environment;
- it facilitates development in vital areas of scientific and technological progress;
- it helps solve employment issues;
- it alleviates social tension and contributes to the democratization of market relations;
- it motivates individuals to realize their creative potential;
- it enables the involvement of socially vulnerable groups in the workforce;
- it improves the qualifications and practical experience of young professionals.

Based on these aspects, the development of small business and private entrepreneurship remains one of the main directions in the consistent continuation of wide-scale reforms and modernization efforts in our republic. One illustrative example of this is the attention given to the agricultural sector. In President Islam Karimov's address at the meeting of the Cabinet of Ministers, dedicated to the results of the country's socio-economic development in 2019 and the key priority directions of the economic program for 2020, it was noted that as a result of the implementation of a comprehensive national program in 2014, approximately one million new jobs were created, about 60 percent of which were in rural areas.

Entrepreneurial activity includes the production of certain goods, the execution of works, and the provision of services. According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Guarantees of Freedom of Entrepreneurial Activity,” entrepreneurship is defined as a proactive activity carried out by entrepreneurial entities under their own property responsibility and legal compliance, aimed at generating income (profit) and accepting associated risks. Several essential conditions and criteria underpin entrepreneurial activity.

First, the entrepreneur integrates production factors in the process of creating goods and services and acts as a “catalyst.”

Second, in the course of running a business, the entrepreneur assumes the complex responsibility of making independent decisions.

Third, as an organizer, the entrepreneur strives to implement new production technologies and create innovative products.

Fourth, an entrepreneur is someone who is not afraid to take risks—not only risking their property, time, and labor but also the capital of partners and shareholders.

Summarizing the various perspectives and definitions regarding entrepreneurship, it can be concisely defined as follows: Entrepreneurship is an economic activity aimed at generating profit and utilizing it efficiently, regardless of the form or field of business.

The execution of entrepreneurial activity requires adherence to the following principles:

Entrepreneurs must be guaranteed legal rights and freedoms to conduct business;

Entrepreneurship may be carried out either directly by the owner or through entities operating based on ownership rights;

A favorable economic and socio-political environment must exist to ensure freedom of economic management;

Various forms and methods of enterprise and resource utilization must be available;

Entrepreneurs should possess specific knowledge, information, and professional training.

Today, a significant share of GDP is generated in this sector. It provides employment for a large portion of the labor force and accounts for more than half of all innovations. Global experience demonstrates that the development of small business is widely used as a strategic instrument of economic policy in numerous countries. For example:

1. it serves as a primary means of ensuring employment;
2. it is a source of innovation potential and technological development;
3. it enables the search for and introduction of new forms of production activity;
4. it contributes to tax revenues (in Germany, nearly half of all taxes are generated by small businesses);
5. it prevents economic decline (as seen in Hungary, the Czech Republic, and Poland);
6. it is closely interlinked with large businesses and forms the foundation of sustainable development and national competitiveness.

The effective policy for developing private entrepreneurship at the regional level can be implemented through the following priority directions, taking into account the specific employment conditions of each region:

- creating new jobs in the sphere of private entrepreneurship based on regional characteristics;
- expanding education and retraining opportunities in entrepreneurship;
- providing information and consulting services to entrepreneurs;
- supporting local initiatives aimed at increasing employment through entrepreneurship;
- encouraging internal mobility and inter-sectoral movement;
- organizing systems for temporary employment;
- facilitating external labor migration, and others.

In the near future, this will have a significant impact on the implementation of targeted regional programs aimed at increasing employment through the support and development of small business and private entrepreneurship, as well as enhancing social welfare. Such attention to these sectors will form the foundation for regional economic development.

Employment policy, as a component of the country's socio-economic development strategy, should be aligned with the transitional stage of the economy and focus on the effective use of labor potential and the resolution of employment-related challenges. It is essential to ensure a socially optimal level of employment through mechanisms of labor redistribution. As is widely recognized, labor market regulation policies are designed to achieve the following objectives:

- to balance labor supply and demand;
- to encourage the unemployed to seek work;
- to improve the professional mobility of job-seeking citizens;
- and to provide employment for everyone actively looking for work.

In Uzbekistan, this function is performed by the State Fund for Employment of the Population. The fund is primarily financed through contributions from enterprises, employees, and entrepreneurs who operate without establishing legal entities. The amount of unemployment benefits is determined either as a percentage of the previous salary or as a fixed amount. On average, the benefit equals 50–60% of the average wage. However, the level of this payment can have both motivating and discouraging effects. Empirical evidence shows that if an unemployed person loses only a small portion of their income, they may delay re-entering the labor market, prolonging the job search until the benefit payments expire.

A more effective and sustainable form of state employment policy is the active employment policy, which aims to stimulate labor demand, create new jobs financed by the employment fund, and provide loans for enterprise-level job creation, thereby contributing to economic stability.

The establishment of a small business ecosystem in Uzbekistan provides the following opportunities:

- utilization of free labor resources, development of new economic relations, emergence of new forms of ownership, and reintegration of workers released from larger enterprises into productive activity;
- improvement of the material, moral, and professional standards of the population, particularly among youth;
- restoration and support of national and traditional crafts, and the development of small and medium-sized enterprises and rural settlements, all of which are crucial for enhancing regional economic efficiency.

While acknowledging the positive role of small business and private entrepreneurship in economic development, it is important not to overstate their potential.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In our view, the organization of labor within entrepreneurial activity must consider the labor costs per unit of time and their structural composition. Among the many challenges that hinder business development, the financial factor is the most critical. The majority of surveyed entrepreneurs emphasized the lack of sufficient financial resources. Any entrepreneur wishing to launch a business requires access to a certain amount of startup capital. Therefore, it is imperative to enhance the role of microfinance institutions in supporting the growth of entrepreneurship.

REFERENCES

1. Botirjon o'g'li, M. B., & Hasanboy o'g'li, S. D. (2022). *Organization and increase of activity of small industrial zones*.
2. Abdullajanovich, U. T. (2022–March). *The role of industrial enterprises in the development of the national economy*. In *Conference Zone* (pp. 271–276).
3. Zayliyev, A. A., Jurayev, E. S., & Muxammadjonov, B. B. (2018). *Disclosure lines of creative financial reporting of trade banks*. *Teoriya i praktika sovremennoy nauki*, (3), 120–122.
4. O'g'li, M. B. B. (2021). *Establishment and activity of small free economic zones in the territory of Uzbekistan*. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*, 1(2), 156–159.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 7

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin. Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>